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Motivational Orientations and Learning Strategies of Engineering Students using MSLQ

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INTRODUCTION

Determining university students' motivational orientations and their use of different learning strategies reveals important characteristics of their self-regulation skills and personal functioning. Psychologists and educational researchers have sought different ways to assess these characteristics e.g., by several questionnaires. One of the most well-known questionnaire is the MSLQ (Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire) that has been developed by Pintrich et al. in 1991 [1]. In this study, goal orientations, control of learning beliefs, self-efficacy for learning performance, resource management strategies as well as cognitive and metacognitive strategies of 62 engineering students from TUT (Tampere University of Technology) have been assessed using an extract of 22 questions from the MSLQ plus five additional queries, which have been formed by the author.

The sample of 62 students consisted of 39 students from the Faculty of Computing and Electrical Engineering, 19 students from the Faculty of Engineering Sciences and 4 students from other faculties of TUT. Most participants were 3rd and 4th year engineering students, although a few 2nd year students participated as well. Data were collected at the beginning of the first lecture of the course *ASE-2411 Introduction to System Operation* in January 2018. The students were informed about the nature of

the self-report test and that the test would have no effect on their final mark. Students rated themselves anonymously using integers on a Likert scale between 1 (“not at all true of me”) and 5 (“very true of me”).

The rating distributions obtained indicate that the goal orientation of the students is mostly intrinsic than extrinsic. The students also have relatively strong control beliefs over their own learning. However, for some reasons, they have only moderate self-efficacy beliefs for learning performance. In addition, students’ use of resource management strategies like scheduling of own learning considerably varies between individuals. Relative large deviations were also observed within learning strategies scales. Nonetheless, the results from the questionnaire gives insight into students’ motivational orientations and their use of learning strategies, which help staff members to gain better understanding of different functioning of students attending to the class.

1 MOTIVATED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING QUESTIONNAIRE

The MSLQ is divided into two sections; namely, to a motivation section and learning strategies section. The intention of the motivation section is to assess students’ goals and value beliefs, whereas the learning strategies section considers students’ use of different cognitive and metacognitive strategies as well as resource management skills. [1] In this study, a collection of factors was formed from both sections of the MSLQ to discover students’ motivational orientations, expectations for success, behaviour in different learning contexts, control of learning beliefs, and ability to regulate own cognitive activities. The factors in this study have been chosen on the basis of how well they have correlated with grades in previous research papers. The chosen factors and the corresponding components are described below.

1.1 Motivation section, its components and selected factors

The motivation section is divided into value, expectancy and affective components. The value component includes measures of intrinsic goal orientation, extrinsic goal orientation and task value. Goal orientation refers to students’ perception of the reasons why he/she is engaging in a learning task. If students have intrinsic goal orientation then they are likely to engage themselves in learning activities for reasons like curiosity, challenge and mastery, while extrinsically oriented students participate for reasons like rewards, grades, performance, evaluation by others and competition. Task value on the other hand refers to students’ evaluation of how interesting, important and useful tasks are for them. High task value should lead to more involvement in students’ learning, because it implies general interest, importance and utility towards learning activities.

The expectancy component consists of control of learning beliefs and self-efficacy for learning and performance. Control of learning beliefs is important, because it refers to students’ beliefs that positive outcomes are more dependent on their own efforts rather than external factors such as teachers. Students should study more strategically and effectively if they feel that they can control their academic performance. Hence, in a class where students display high values of control of learning beliefs, teaching and

learning relationship should be arranged to emphasize active student engagement and responsibility. Furthermore, control of learning beliefs interact with self-efficacy beliefs, which predicts well students' motivation and learning [2].

Self-efficacy for learning and performance assess two expectancy factors: expectancy for success and self-efficacy. Expectancy for success considers performance related things like good grades, whereas self-efficacy refers to student's self-appraisal of his/her ability to accomplish a task and his/her confidence in his/her own skills to perform a task. Self-efficacy for learning and performance has generally been found to correlate well with academic achievement [3; 4].

The affective component of MSLQ measures test anxiety, which has been found to have negative influence on expectancies and learning performance. Test anxiety has two components: a cognitive component, which refers to student's negative thoughts that distract performance during tests, and an emotionality component, which refers to physiological causes of anxiety. Practicing effective learning strategies reduces degree of anxiety, but students seldom use strategies despite of training [5].

The chosen factors from each component of the motivation section that are used in this study are listed below. The resulting mean μ and standard deviation s rounded to two significant digits have been placed in the parentheses at the end of each factor. Interested readers may examine each factor graphically using the following link: <https://padlet.com/pyrhonen/wcpwdta0n96p>

Component: **Value**

- Factor: **Intrinsic goal orientation**: "I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn". ($\mu = 3.90, s = 0.82$)
- Factor: **Extrinsic goal orientation**: "Getting a good grade is the most satisfying thing for me". ($\mu = 2.90, s = 0.93$)
- Factor: **Task value**: "Understanding the subject matter of courses is very important to me". ($\mu = 4.00, s = 0.71$)

Component: **Expectancy**

- Factor: **Control of learning belief**: "If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the material in this course". ($\mu = 4.20, s = 0.69$)
- Factor: **Self-efficacy for learning and performance**: "I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this class". ($\mu = 3.00, s = 0.80$)
- Factor: **Self-efficacy for learning and performance**: "I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in this class". ($\mu = 2.80, s = 0.93$)
- Factor: **Self-efficacy for learning and performance**: "I'm confident I can understand the basic concepts taught in this course". ($\mu = 4.40, s = 0.66$)
- Factor: **Self-efficacy for learning and performance**: "I'm confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests in this course". ($\mu = 3.10, s = 0.78$)
- Factor: **Self-efficacy for learning and performance**: "I expect to do well in this class". ($\mu = 3.50, s = 0.65$)

Component: **Affective**

- Factor: **Test anxiety**: “When I take a test, I think about how poorly I am doing compared with other students”. ($\mu = 1.80, s = 1.10$)
- Factor: **Test anxiety**: “I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam”. ($\mu = 2.10, s = 1.00$)
- Factor: **Test anxiety**: “When I take tests, I think of the consequences of failing”. ($\mu = 2.00, s = 1.10$)

1.2 Learning strategies section and selected factors

The learning strategies section is composed of cognitive and metacognitive strategies, and resource management strategies subsections. Cognitive and metacognitive strategies subsection measures student’s use of basic rehearsal, elaboration and organization strategies, which help students to connect new information to prior knowledge. The subsection also measures student’s use of metacognitive self-regulation activities, which are composed of three processes; namely, planning, monitoring and regulating.

Planning, such as goal setting and task analysis, assists in activating students to learn new material and to work with upcoming challenges. Monitoring activities like self-testing help students in understanding the material and connecting it with prior knowledge. Regulation refers to continuous adjustment of one’s cognitive activities like changing one’s way to study in the face of obstacles or other difficulties. Regulating activities improve learning performance by helping students to check and correct their behaviour when needed. Inability to regulate have been found to be a major inhibition to student’s success in academic activities and life in general. [6–8]

The resource management subsection measures students’ ability to manage time and study environments, which are now becoming more and more important because of digitalization. Time management include scheduling and planning one’s time use efficiently, whereas study environment management refers to one’s ability to organize a good place to study for oneself. The following factors from the learning strategies section has been used in this study.

Cognitive and metacognitive strategies: **Elaboration**

- “I try to relate ideas in this subject to those in other courses whenever possible”. ($\mu = 3.40, s = 1.10$)

Cognitive and metacognitive strategies: **Organization**

- “When I study for this course, I go through the readings and my class notes and try to find the most important ideas”. ($\mu = 3.30, s = 1.10$)

Cognitive and metacognitive strategies: **Metacognitive self-regulation**

- “During class time I often miss important points because I’m thinking of other things”. ($\mu = 3.00, s = 0.95$)

- “I often find that I have been reading for class but don’t know what it was all about”. ($\mu = 2.60, s = 0.75$)
- “I try to think through a topic and decide what I am supposed to learn from it rather than just reading it over when studying”. ($\mu = 3.00, s = 0.92$)

Resource management strategies: **Time and study environment**

- “I usually study in a place where I can concentrate on my course work”. ($\mu = 4.00, s = 0.93$)
- “I find it hard to stick to a study schedule”. ($\mu = 2.40, s = 1.00$)
- “I rarely find time to review my notes or readings before an exam”. ($\mu = 2.00, s = 1.00$)

Resource management strategies: **Effort regulation**

- “I work hard to do well even if I don’t like what we are doing”. ($\mu = 3.50, s = 0.95$)
- “When course work is difficult, I give up or only study the easy parts”. ($\mu = 2.10, s = 0.84$)

In addition to the above, the following supplementary items were added to the questionnaire by the author:

Supplementary items:

- “I schedule my studies”. ($\mu = 2.90, s = 1.10$)
- “I like to study on my own”. ($\mu = 3.50, s = 0.92$)
- “I like to study with my friends”. ($\mu = 3.10, s = 1.00$)
- “I set goals for my studies”. ($\mu = 3.50, s = 0.99$)
- “If I could decide, I would choose other means for course evaluation than final exams and midterms”. ($\mu = 3.10, s = 1.20$)

The above items attempt to determine student’s learning preferences in individual and peer contexts, intention for goal setting and scheduling, and preferences for alternative ways for course evaluation as opposed to traditional examination. Currently, universities and higher education institutes are moving towards competence-based curricula in which students are evaluated by much more versatile ways than before, and, as such, have likely affected to students’ needs and expectations. In addition, group working, collaborative problem solving, and other socially shared learning activities are fairly standard these days in higher education. Hence, it is justifiable to evaluate how students concern these factors in their own studies.

2 ANALYSIS OF SELECTED ANSWER DISTRIBUTIONS

In this section, the rating distributions of specifically chosen factors are briefly analysed. The analysed factors have been chosen either because the answer distributions represent prominent heterogeneity among individual students, or because the chosen factors are known to have relatively strong correlation e.g., with final grades.

Goal orientation and Task value: The goal orientation of the students seems to be much more intrinsic than extrinsic, which indicate that students pursue in academic activities for their own sake rather than attaining something from them. High values of intrinsic goal orientation are known to lead better results compared with extrinsically oriented motivation. Furthermore, students also display high task value, which indicate intrinsic interest towards learning activities. Usually, high intrinsic motivation leads to high task value.

Control of learning belief: Students seem to belief that their own efforts will lead to positive outcomes in contrast with external factors such as the teacher. This is a positive sign, because students feel that their own efforts to learn can make desired changes in their learning.

Self-efficacy for learning and performance: Students' expectancy for success is generally moderate, but high expectancy is obtained as regards to students' confidence in understanding the basic concepts taught in the class ($\mu = 4.40$, $s = 0.66$). Students' beliefs for receiving an excellent grade in this class is however significantly lower ($\mu = 3.00$, $s = 0.8$). Furthermore, students' expectancy for doing well in this class measures $\mu = 3.50$, $s = 0.65$. "Doing well" is a subjective matter and links to individual preferences and to perceptions on how "well" is interpreted among individual students. It should be noted that uncertainty in several different forms is involved within expectancy factors: A student may be uncertain regarding to his/her own abilities to accomplish a class based on his/her previous experiences and achievements. A class may have reputation of being difficult among the students, which may lower the degree of all expectancy factors. A student may not expect anything from the class, nor from himself/herself, which may result in more or less random answers or answers that lie in the middle of the scale.

Test anxiety: About 10% of students expressed that taking tests raises negative emotions that distract performance, and 15% spend time thinking about consequences of failing while they are taking tests. Such cognitive concern and preoccupation have been found to be one of the greatest sources of performance decrement. In this sense, 15% is relatively large percentage among 3rd and 4th year engineering students.

Elaboration and Organization: These factors from cognitive and metacognitive strategies subsection display large deviations, and hence, wide heterogeneity among students. It is unknown why such large deviation exists between students. However, it does indicate that some students use much stronger learning strategies, while others hardly use any strategies. Strong learning strategies are known to reduce e.g., test anxiety. Learning strategies also help students to store information in long-term memory and constructing connections between important information that has been learned, which, on the other hand, have positive influence e.g., on performance expectations. [1]

Metacognitive self-regulation: Students seem to be aware when they lose track during class time or during learning on their own. Surprisingly many do get lost during e.g., lectures, because they are thinking other things. Reasons that cause students to think something else during classes remain unknown in this study. Nonetheless, awareness of such events is not sufficient as regards to ability to regulate own cognition; rather, students should be capable of adjusting own activities based on their progress monitoring skills as well as on personal evaluations e.g., whether a chosen solution strategy has resulted in positive outcomes. Finally, planning activities like goal setting also indicate heterogeneity: almost 20% of students study with almost no intention on goal setting.

Time and study environment: Students rate themselves relatively skilled as regards to setting up a good place to study. Conversely, time management skills and ability to schedule own work show fairly large deviations. For example, the supplementary item: "I schedule my studies" show that almost 40% of students hardly schedule their studies at all!

Effort regulation: Effort regulation factors show that majority of students do not give up easily when they face difficulties or uninteresting tasks. Effort regulation is an important self-management skill in academic life, because it emphasizes commitment, and it produces completeness even if distractions occur.

Supplementary items: An interesting observation can be made from students' answers regarding to study preferences in individual and collaborative settings: students generally like to study both on their own and with their friends, but they clearly prefer more individual settings. However, most of the students do not have a clear opinion for either of the options, because most of the answers lie around the mean value of the distributions. There might be some level of uncertainty involved in these opinions owing to the previous experiences that students have gained e.g., in earlier courses. Finally, students' preferences for alternative ways for course evaluation as opposed to traditional exams are much dispersed: large portion of students seem to prefer exams while almost equal amount of students would choose other means of evaluation. One possibility to meet such needs is to offer different options for course evaluation for students to choose from.

3 COMMENTARY

Several important factors regarding to 3rd year engineering students' motivational orientations and learning strategies were rated in this study. However, the data obtained only indicate the state of the current situation. There are no data from the beginning of the studies, and hence, no information available on how these factors have been evolved during the previous study years. It is also impossible to predict changes of these factors that will occur in the future. Therefore, it would be reasonable to organize one or two longitudinal inquiries to find out how students' key regulatory skills and processes develop during university studies. In addition, different study paths with other courses may lead to diversified development of self-regulation skills.

Nonetheless, students in this study are generally intrinsically motivated, and they show high task value and strong control of learning beliefs. Unfortunately, expectancy for success and self-efficacy display somewhat low values. Furthermore, ratings for learning strategies factors and especially for self-regulation skills considerably varies between individual students. It certainly seems that students are willing to learn, but they may be unaware how they should learn, *as individuals*, and how to control their own learning processes and cognition. Many lack fundamental metacognitive skills such as planning, monitoring and regulation skills, which may degrade their academic performance, and hence, undermine their possibilities to develop essential life-long learning skills.

Furthermore, increasing uncertainty and rapidly changing world demand ability to tolerate changes and adaptive skills, which both require well-developed self-regulatory processes, volition and ability to control emotions. Hence, teachers may need to reconsider the design and organisation of their teaching and learning practices, if they attempt to foster the development of important self-regulated learning processes of students and prepare them for the upcoming challenges occurring in the future. An alternative possibility to improve these essential qualities of life could be mentoring. In TUT, a mentoring program has just begun, which is partly based on the MSLQ manual.

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